

Folklore medicinal applications of fauna in the vicinity of Harighel, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

There is a dearth of knowledge on the scope of this sector and its impact on the species involved. Touching, petting, viewing, and working with animal species such as vertebrates are beneficial to one's health. Their role in general practices is interconnected with therapeutic usage, as well as illness inhibition. Data on ethnomedicinal applications of animals were gathered. The study's major goal was to learn about the traditional medicinal practices of the people of Harighel, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. During the years 2018-2020, data on ethnomedicinal and ethnocultural applications of animals were gathered. 100 respondents completed semi-structured interviews and questionnaires. Informants were chosen based on their ethnomedicinal understanding of herptiles and fishes' traditional medicinal and cultural significance. Total 26 animal species with different body parts (i.e. fat, meat, skin, egg, milk and whole body) were used to treat 19 different diseases.

Keywords: Folklore, Ethnomedicine, Harighel, Pakistan

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INTRODUCTION

Pakistan southernmost border is connected with the Arabian Sea; and its northernmost point is located in the vast Himalayas. The peaks in the north, west, and northwest are a confluence of three mountain ranges: the Hindukush, the Himalayas, and the Karakorum. Pakistan includes about 225 wetlands and 19 Ramsar sites, as well as the country's biggest river system. Because of the dramatic variations in elevation, Pakistan offers a diverse range of species (Khan, 2006; Altaf *et al.*, 2014).

The Animal is widely used in medicine, but there is a dearth of comprehensive knowledge on the scope of this sector and its impact on the species involved. It has been proven that touching, petting, viewing, and working with animal species such as vertebrates are beneficial to one's health. These techniques reduce heart rate and stroke risk. Animal-based compounds derived from various animal species are utilized as traditional medicines, accounting for approximately 8.7% of the extremely significant chemicals employed in the current health-care system (Santos-Fita *et al.*, 2009; Mendonça *et al.*, 2014; Altaf

et al., 2020). In comparison to plant species, animal-based goods are still disregarded. Residents of rural regions rely more on animal-based items since they have a good understanding of zoo treatments. Animals, both wild and domesticated, are vital to humans. However, wild animal species are threatened by anthropogenic activities such as banned hunting for decorative purposes, food, medicine, deforestation, agricultural expansion, industrialization and urbanization (Santos-Fita *et al.*, 2009; Rômulo *et al.*, 2012; Altaf, 2016; Altaf *et al.*, 2017a; Altaf *et al.*, 2018).

Species of animals are commonly used in traditional general medications. Their role in general practices is interconnected with therapeutic usage, as well as illness inhibition, which has been documented in numerous social-cultural zones across the world. For a long time, people mistreated the oil, blood, flesh, eggs, shells, bones, and skin of animals to furnish sustenance and materials for crafting attractive tools and magical artifacts. Despite all of these uses, the herpetofauna is still employed for cultural and therapeutic purposes, as well as day-to-day activities (Alves *et al.*, 2012; Mendonça *et al.*, 2014; Altaf *et al.*, 2020).

Herptiles are well-known as one of the most fascinating and vital animal species. Herptiles are utilized in ethnomedicine and folklore to heal ailments in many cultures (Khan, 1999; Alves and Rosa, 2007; Rômulo *et al.*, 2012; Hussain *et al.*, 2015). Apart from a few publications on ethnozoology or zoo-therapies, traditional applications of animal species to heal illnesses in human beings and other fauna have been described in Pakistan (Haider *et al.*, 2017; Hakeem *et al.*, 2017; Khan *et al.*, 2017; Muhammad *et al.*, 2017a; Muhammad *et al.*, 2017b; Muhammad *et al.*, 2017c; Rauf *et al.*, 2017; Umair *et al.*, 2017; Aslam and Faiz, 2020; Ijaz *et al.*, 2020; Mughal *et al.*, 2020; Saleem *et al.*, 2021; Saeed *et al.*, 2022; Umair *et al.*, 2022). The study's major goal was to learn about the traditional medicinal practices of the people of Harighel, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

Harighel is found in the lower Himalayas. The research region is located in a damp environment with monsoon access. The changes in altitude cause a slew of differences in rainfall and humidity in various sections of the region. The summer is mild, with an average temperature of 37°C, while the winter is bitterly cold, with an average temperature of 4°C. The average rainfall was measured to be 150mm (Figure 1) (DRU, 2007; Bibi *et al.*, 2013).

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

During the years 2018-2020, data on ethnomedicinal and ethnocultural applications of animals were gathered. 100 respondents completed semi-structured interviews and questionnaires. Informants were chosen based on their ethnomedicinal understanding of herptiles and fishes' traditional medicinal and cultural significance. Data were statistically documented utilizing indices i.e. “Relative popularity level”, “rank order priority” and “similarity index”.

Figure 1: Map of the study area.

RELATIVE POPULARITY LEVEL (RPL)

RPL was analyzed prior to study (Altaf *et al.*, 2017b; Altaf *et al.*, 2020; Rahman *et al.*, 2022). Animals were divided into two categories: "popular" and "unpopular." Popular animals are those for which more than half of the maximum frequency of citation was specified "FC". (ii) The creatures that were left behind were documented as unpopular. While a horizontal line was fictitious for popular animals, the average no. of uses per animal is independent of the "frequency of citation", who recognizes the animals; thus, the average no. of utilizes of a "popular" animal species does not increase with the addition to the frequency of citation that cites the animals for any ethnopharmacological use. The "RPL" was picked to one of the popular animals (1.0). The relative popularity level no. for animals in the unpopular category is less than 1.0.

RANK ORDER PRIORITY (ROP)

ROP is observed to worth of animals (Altaf *et al.*, 2017b; Altaf *et al.*, 2020; Rahman *et al.*, 2022) and given formula is utilized;

$$ROP = FL \times RPL$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

ETHNOGRAPHY

All population in this area is Muslim, so data were collected from the Muslims male (n=84) and female (n=16). Lot of Inhabitants were connected with rural, therefore most of data were gathered from peri-urban areas and left over from urban. The informers have different occupations as; government employers, teachers, housewives, students, farmer, shopkeepers and traditional healers from study area. Lot of informers were well-educated (92.9%) and remaining was illiterate. Most of the respondents were below 60, while the lowest respondents (n=18) were belong above 60 in study area (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Respondents profile of the study area.

ETHNOMEDICINAL APPLICATION OF ANIMAL FAUNA

The inhabitants of the study area have ethnopharmacological information and use animals to cure various disorders. Total 26 animal species with different body parts (i.e. fat, meat, skin, egg, milk and whole body) (Figure 3) were used to treat 19 different diseases viz. snake bite, antibacterial, antifungal, boil, cough, diabetic, enhance memory, eyes diseases, remove warts, skin infection, ulcer, male impotency, backbone pain, bone strength, fever, joint pain, skin diseases, weakness and paralysis (Figure 4). Nutritional deficiency and inbreeding may attribute in high prevalence of these illnesses in Harighel, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan.

BODY PARTS

All 48 diseases were treated with 12 different body parts of wild animal's species viz. fat, meat, skin, egg, milk and whole body (Figure 4.2). Animal meat was the highest employed (n=10) body part, next were as fat, milk, egg, hair, whole body, honey and skin (9, 4, 2, 2, 1, 1 and 1 respectively). It has been reported that "omega-3 fatty acid" in animal fats reduces irritation (Wilson, 2015). These used

were documented in earlier to treat thrombotic, CNS and old agr problems (Breteler, 2000; Haag, 2003). Animal milk has high level of proteins, as well as vitamins used to cure joint pain and enhance strength and power in body (Hemme *et al.*, 2010; Alabdulkarim, 2012; Sabahelkhier *et al.*, 2012; Contarini and Povolo, 2013; Vats and Thomas, 2015).

Figure 3: Body parts of animals used in diseases.

Figure 4: The diseases cured by traditional medicinal.

ETHNOPHARMACOLOGICAL APPLICATIONS OF ANIMALS

It is documented that fat of *Bungarus caeruleus caeruleus* used against snake bite and previously it is reported against anti-venom (Arshad *et al.*, 2014). It is documented that fat of *Doboa russelii russelii* is used against snake bite and previously it is reported against Eye sight, urination, stool, flatus, anti-venom

(Benarjee *et al.*, 2010; Arshad *et al.*, 2014; Aloufi and Eid, 2016). It is documented that fat of *Laudakia agrorensis* is used against weakness, backbone and joint pain. It is documented that fat of *Varanus bengalensis* is used against backbone pain, joint pain and male impotency.

It is documented that meat of *Columba livia* is used against paralysis. It is documented that meat of *Streptopelia orientalis* is used against paralysis and previously it is reported against maturity, sexual problems (Aloufi and Eid, 2016; Altaf *et al.*, 2017a). It is documented that meat of *Spilopelia chinensis* is used against paralysis and enhance of memory. It is documented that meat and egg of *Passer domesticus* is used against paralysis and fever.

It is documented that meat of *Passer cinnamomeus* is used against paralysis and fever and previously it is reported against paralysis (Kiran Rauf and Iftikhar, 2017). It is documented that meat and egg of *Gallus gallus domesticus* is used against fever. It is documented that feather of *Anas platyrhynchos domesticus* is used against skin infection. It is documented that fat of *Sancus murinus* is used against joint pain and previously it is reported against. It is documented that hair of *Hystrix indica* is used against boil. It is documented that fat of *Macaca mulatta* is used against skin disease and previously it is reported against weakness and asthma (Padmanabhan and Sujana, 2008). It is documented that fat of *Canis aureus* is used against skin diseases. It is documented that fat of *Vulpes vulpes* is used against Male impotency and previously it is reported against healing pus in lungs and ear diseases (Lev, 2003; Yeshe *et al.*, 2017). It is documented that Milk and Meat of *Capra aegagrus hircus* is used against Bone strength. It is documented that Milk and Meat of *Bos taurus* is used against Bone strength. It is documented that hairs of *Equus caballus* is used against removal of warts. It is documented that milk of *Camelus dromedaries* is used against diabetic and previously it is reported against acidity, hepatitis B and C (Jaroli *et al.*, 2010; Arshad *et al.*, 2014). It is documented that milk and meat of *Bubalus bubalis* is used against bone strength. It is documented that whole body of *Apporactodea spp.* is used against backbone pain, antibacterial, antifungal. It is documented that honey of *Apis spp.* is used against skin diseases (Table 1).

FREQUENCY OF CITATION (FC)

It is noted that the highest frequency of citation (i.e. FC=22) is noted for *Passer domesticus* and *Passer cinnamomeus*. While the lowest frequency of citation (i.e. FC=1) is noted for *Sancus murinus* and *Hystrix indica* (Table 1).

RELATIVE POPULARITY LEVEL (RPL)

It is noted that the highest RPL is noted for *Passer domesticus* and *Passer cinnamomeus*, while the lowest is noted for *Sancus murinus* and *Hystrix indica* (Table 1).

RANK ORDER PRIORITY (ROP)

It is noted that the highest RPL is noted for *Passer domesticus* and *Passer cinnamomeus*, while the lowest is noted for *Sancus murinus* and *Hystrix indica* (Table 1).

CONCLUSION

Folklore animal-based-medicinal concept of communities of Harighel, it is indication; inhabitants have high connection with living creature. Furthermore, application of 26 species of fauna were applied to heal diseases in *Homo sapiens* have not been documented earlier. This study gives data that might be worthy for protection of animal diversity in study area of AJ&K.

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Table 1: Ethnopharmacological knowledge among the Kashmiri people of Harighel, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan.

Sr.	Common name	PU=MA	Medicinal uses	Code	FC	RPL	ROP
Herptiles							
1	<i>Bungarus caeruleus caeruleus</i> Schneider, 1801 Common krait Kala sup	Fat=Topical	Snake bite	DC1	2	0.22	0.44

2	<i>Daboia russeli irusselii</i> Shaw and Nodder, 1797 Russell's chain viper Sap	Fat=Topical	Snake bite	DR1	2	0.22	0.44
3	<i>Laudakia agrorensis</i> Stoliczka, 1872 Agror agama Sandaila	Fat=Topical	Weakness	LA1	3	0.33	1.00
			Backbone pain	LA2	3	0.33	1.00
			Joint pain	LA3	3	0.33	1.00
4	<i>Varanus bengalensis</i> Daudin, 1802 Bengal monitor Kehskarow	Fat=Topical	Backbone pain	VB1	3	0.33	1.00
			Joint pain	VB2	3	0.33	1.00
			Male impotency	VB3	3	0.33	1.00
5	<i>Naja oxiana</i> Eichwald, 1837 Brown cobra Chajla sup	Skin=Topical	Eyes diseases	NO1	2	0.22	0.44
Birds							
6	<i>Coturnix coturnix</i> (Linnaeus, 1758 Common quail Batair	Meat=Oral	Paralysis	CC1	8	0.89	7.11
			Weakness	CC2	8	0.89	7.11
	<i>Columba livia</i> (Gmelin, 1789) Common Pigeon JungliKabotar	Meat=Oral	Paralysis	CL1	10	1.11	11.11
7							
8	<i>Streptopelia orientalis</i> (Latham, 1790) Oriental Turtle Dove Fakhta	Meat=Oral	Paralysis	SO1	10	1.11	11.11
	<i>Spilopelia chinensis</i> (Scopoli, 1786) Spotted Dove Fakhta	Meat=Oral	Paralysis	SC1	10	1.11	11.11
9			Enhance memory	SC2	1	0.11	0.11
	<i>Passer domesticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) House Sparrow Chiri	Meat and Egg=Oral	Paralysis	PD1	22	2.44	53.78
10			Fever	PD2	22	2.44	53.78
	<i>Passer cinnamomeus</i> (Tessminck, 1836) Russet Sparrow Jungli Chiri	Meat=Oral	Paralysis	PC1	22	2.44	53.78
11			Fever	PC2	22	2.44	53.78

12	<i>Gallus gallus domesticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) Hen Murghi	Meat and egg=Oral	Fever	GG1	21	2.33	49.00
13	<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i> <i>domesticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) Duck Batakh	Feather=Oral	Skin infection	AP1	20	2.22	44.44
Mammals							
14	<i>Panthera pardus</i> Linnaeus, 1758 Common Leopard Cheetah/tanduwa	Fat=Topical	Weakness	PP1	9	1.00	9.00
15	<i>Suncus murinus</i> Linnaeus, 1758 House Shrew Choa	Fat=Topical	Joint pain	SM1	1	0.11	0.11
16	<i>Hystrix indica</i> Kerr, 179 Indian Crested Porcupine, Say	Hair= Topical	Boil	HI1	1	0.11	0.11
17	<i>Macaca mulatta</i> Zimmermann, 1780 Rhesus Macaque Bndar/Bojo	Fat= Topical	Skin diseases	MM1	1	0.11	0.11
18	<i>Canis aureus</i> Linnaeus, 1758 Asiatic jackal Gedar	Fat= Topical	Skin diseases	CA1	2	0.22	0.44
19	<i>Vulpes vulpes</i> Linnaeus, 1758 Red fox Phand	Fat= Topical	Male impotency	VV1	2	0.22	0.44
20	<i>Capra aegagrus hircus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) Goat Bakri	Milk and Meat=Oral	Bone strength	CC1	11	1.22	13.44
21	<i>Bos taurus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) Cow	Milk and Meat=Oral	Bone strength	BT1	21	2.33	49.00

	Gay						
22	<i>Equus caballus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) Horse Ghura	Hairs	Remove warts	EC1	23	2.56	58.78
23	<i>Camelus dromedaries</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) Camel	Milk	Diabetic	CD1	19	2.11	40.11
24	<i>Bubalus bubalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) Buffalo Maj	Milk and Meat=Oral	Bone strength	BB1	21	2.33	49.00
		Invertebrates					
25	<i>Apporactodea spp.</i> Savigny, 1826 Earthworm	Whole body=Oral	Backbone Pain	AP1	7	0.78	5.44
			Antibacterial	AP2	7	0.78	5.44
			Antifungal	AP3	7	0.78	5.44
26	<i>Apis spp.</i> Linnaeus, 1758 European honey bee Shahd Makhi	Honey=Oral	Skin diseases	AS1	14	1.56	21.78
